

(C-O-C) and 555 cm^{-1} (CBr); δ 2.60 (2H, d, 3-H), 4.40 (9H, m, 7-OC₄H₉), 5.20 (1H, m, 2-H), 7.0-7.6 (m, ArH) and 7.80 (1H, s, 5-H).

Similarly, other flavanones were prepared (4b-1; Table 1).

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Synthesis of Cyclic Ketones by Activated Nitriles†

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THE use of cyano compounds in organic synthesis is now receiving considerable interest. As a part of our program of developing new, simple and efficient procedure for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds using readily available nitrile-containing intermediates¹⁻⁶, the synthesis of cyclohexan-1,3-dione derivatives using acrylonitrile as starting material has now been achieved and is reported herein.

Thus, when acrylonitrile was treated with the ketones (1a-d) in alkaline medium a product (2) was

obtained whose structure was assigned on the basis of its conversion to the semicarbazone derivatives (4). Hydrolysis and estrification in one-step reaction of δ -ketonitriles (2a-d) resulted in the formation of the corresponding δ -ketoester (5a-d). Structure 5 was established based on elemental analysis and ir spectrum which showed well-defined bands attributable for C=O (ester at 1710 and ketonic at 1690 cm^{-1}). The δ -ketoester (5) was readily cyclised into cyclohexan-1,3-dione derivatives (6) on heating with alcoholic sodium methoxide. Structure 6 was confirmed by analytical and ir spectral data which showed well-defined bands at 1740 cm^{-1} attributable to cyclic C=O. The structures of 6 were further confirmed by preparing (i) the 2-phenylazo derivatives (7a, b, d) in three cases (from 6a, b, d, respectively), (ii) bis-(2,6-diketo-3-phenylcyclohexyl) methane (8) by condensing with benzaldehyde and (iii) the 2-bromo derivative (9) by bromination of 6d.

The cyanoethylation reaction of the ketones (1) with acrylonitrile can be considered as a novel route for the synthesis of not only cyclic ketones but also for the synthesis of bicyclic ketones. Thus, it was found that heating of cyclohexanone-2-methylpropionate in alcoholic sodium methoxide afforded bicyclo[1,3,3]nonan-2,9-dione (10). Structure 10 was established on the basis of analytical and spectral data, which showed band at 1740 cm^{-1} (CO).

Experimental

4-Phenyl-4-acetylbutyronitrile (2d): Sodium metal (0.46 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in benzyl methyl ketone (100 g, 0.7 mol) at 90° , then acrylonitrile (28 g, 0.52 mol) was added dropwise within 20 min at $50-60^\circ$. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min, then cooled and neutralised with glacial acetic acid (3 ml) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure to give the product (69%), b.p. $160-61^\circ/10\text{ mm}$ (lit.⁶ $170-72^\circ/12\text{ mm}$); semicarbazone derivative (4d), m.p. 160° (ethanol).

Methyl 4-phenyl-4-acetylbutyrate (5d): A mixture of 2d (0.4 mol) and anhydrous methanol (200 ml) saturated with dry HCl gas was stirred and left to stand overnight, then cooled to 0° , diluted with water and extracted with benzene. The organic layer was washed in turn with water, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure to give the product (60%), b.p. $142-44^\circ/4\text{ mm}$ (lit.⁶ $112-14^\circ/0.1\text{ mm}$).

Similarly, the methyl ester of 4-acetylbutyronitrile⁷, 4-acetylvaleronitrile⁸ and 4-acetyl-4-propylbutyronitrile⁹ were prepared (Table 1).

4-Phenylcyclohexan-1, 3-dione (6d): To a solution of sodium methoxide (0.05 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was added 5d (0.05 mol) and refluxed with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled, neutralised with H_2SO_4 (30 ml; 2N) and the excess methanol

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF α -KETOESTER (5)

Compd. no	R	b.p./mm (°C)	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)	
			C	H
5a	H	80–83/7	58.29 (58.38)	8.54 (8.40)
5b	CH ₃	85–90/8	60.53 (60.31)	8.50 (8.93)
5c	n-C ₃ H ₇	95–100/5 ¹	64.32 (64.51)	9.43 (9.67)
5d	C ₆ H ₅	155–160/7		
5e	2-(2'-Methoxycarbonylethyl)cyclohexanone	120–125/10		

was removed under reduced pressure. To the residue, water (10 ml) was added and extracted with ether (30 ml). The extract was worked up with 20% cold sodium hydroxide and then acidified with 20% H₂SO₄ to give the diketone as oily material. The oily product was again extracted with ether, dried (sodium sulphate) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting oily residue was triturated with acetone to give the product as a solid (60%), m.p. ⁶ 112°.

Cyclohexan-1,3-dione (6a): Other cyclohexanones were obtained in a similar fashion. Thus, 6a, yellow oil, solidified on cooling for long time, (80%), m.p. 102°; 6b, b.p. 130–32°/7 mm (lit.¹⁰ 111°/0.025 mm); 6c (60%), m.p. 73°.

2-Phenylazocyclohexan-1,3-dione (7a): To a solution of 6a (0.05 mol) in 10% sodium hydroxide

(10 ml), was added dropwise with continuous stirring a cold solution of benzene diazonium chloride (0.15 g, 7 ml HCl, 0.1 g sodium nitrite). After cooling for 2 h the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature when a yellow solid was obtained, m.p. 130° (ethanol) (lit.¹⁰ 135°); λ_{max} (methanol) 245, 390 nm (log ϵ 3.27, 4.26).

2-Phenylazo-4-methylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (7b): It was prepared similarly from 6b and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 114° (Found: C, 66.70; H, 6.21. C₁₃H₁₄N₂O₂ calcd. for: C, 66.10; H, 6.06%; λ_{max} (methanol) 245, 390 nm (log ϵ 3.27, 4.26).

2-Phenylazo-4-phenylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (7d): It was prepared similarly from 6d and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 128° (Found: C, 73.83; H, 5.50. C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₂ calcd. for: C, 73.9; H, 5.52%; λ_{max} (methanol) 245, 390 nm (log ϵ 4.10, 4.37).

Phenylbis-(2,6-diketo-3-phenylcyclohexyl)methane (8): To a solution (25 ml; 4%) of 6d in ethanol (50 ml; 50%), was added benzaldehyde (5 drops). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 9.5 h, then left at room temperature for 3 days to give a solid (65%), m.p. 161° (Found: C, 79.53; H, 6.20. C₁₂H₂₈O₄ calcd. for: C, 79.62; H, 6.25%).

2-Bromo-4-phenylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (9): To 6d (0.05 mol) in cold water (200 ml), was added dropwise bromine (0.06 mol) and heated to obtain homogeneous solution. The reaction mixture was cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (Found: C, 59.13; H, 3.95. C₁₂H₁₀BrO₂ calcd. for: C, 59.96; H, 4.15%).

Bicyclo-1,3,3-nonan-2,9-dione (10): It was obtained by the previous general method from 2-(2-methoxy-carbonyl)ethyl)cyclohexanone, (65%), m.p. 141° (Found: C, 71.31; H, 8.46. C₉H₂O₂ calcd. for: C, 72.05; 3.55%; λ_{\max} 254 nm (log ϵ 3.72).

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Aflatoxin Analogues as Possible Anti-coagulants. Part-II

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THE striking characteristic feature of all the aflatoxins which are a group of highly oxygenated and unsaturated compounds, is the presence of di(or tetra)hydro[2,3-*b*]benzofuran¹ structural unit fused to 2-oxopyran unit², which had not been previously noticed in the field of natural products. Some years ago, we reported³ the synthesis of some analogues of aflatoxins containing 4-hydroxycoumarin moiety. We present here the synthesis and anticoagulant activity of some new analogues of aflatoxins.

The active intermediate synthesised (Scheme 1) was 6*a*,9*a*-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3*H*-furo(3',2' : 4,5)-furo[2,3-*f*]benzopyran-3,8-(7*H*)-dione (3). The synthetic strategy envisaged for construction of 3 was to start from 2,3,3*a*,8*a*-tetrahydro-2-oxo-4-benzyloxy-6-methoxy-furo[2,3-*b*]benzofuran (1),

whose synthesis was reported earlier⁴. It was subjected to demethylation, by its treatment with dry pyridine hydrochloride⁵ in order to convert into the corresponding hydroxy compound (2). For the construction of 4-hydroxycoumarin unit upon 2, the feasibility of two different general routes was considered. In one of the routes, the hydroxy was converted into the malonic ester and later was cyclised⁶ by AlCl₃. In the other method, the hydroxy was directly cyclised⁷ into the required heterocycle by using POCl₃ and ZnCl₂. The second method was found to be more suitable and was made use of in the present investigation for obtaining 3. It also became possible to convert 3 into different dicoumarol derivatives (4*a*–*d*). Thus when formaldehyde, aromatic aldehydes and heteroaryl aldehydes were allowed to react with 3, a number of 2,2'-[substituted-methylene]-bis-[6*b*, 9*a*-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3*H*-furo(3',2' : 4,5)-furo[2,3-*f*](1)benzopyran-3,8(7*H*)-diones] (4*a*–*d*), were produced.

The investigations upon structure-pharmacological activity relations of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives revealed that electrophilic substituents like aminomethyl and α -acetylbenzyl groups in position-3, increase the anticoagulant activity⁹. A logical extension of this work would be the Mannich reactions of difuro-4-hydroxycoumarin (3) with formaldehyde and various amines¹⁰. Thus 2-(diphenylaminomethyl)-6*b*,9*a*-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3*H*-furo(3',2' : 4,5)-furo[2,3-*f*](1)benzopyran-3,8(7*H*)-dione (5) was prepared. Similarly, a warfarin analogue of aflatoxins 6 was also synthesised by Micheal addition of an α,β -unsaturated ketone namely benzalacetone¹¹ upon 3. Also a coumarinochromone derivative (7) of the reactive intermediate (3) was obtained by a reaction between 3 and *o*-bromobenzoic acid in the presence of cupric chloride and organic base like pyridine¹².

All the structures have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, uv, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. These compounds exhibit general uv absorption bands at 225, 275 and 310 nm (cinnamoyl chromophore) which are similar to the spectra of aflatoxins¹³. These bands are slightly shifted in basic medium and located around 217, 242(s), 275(s), 280(m) and 302(s)¹⁴. The ir spectra include absorptions around 1785, 1760 and 1688 cm⁻¹, indicating the *cis*-fusion of the five-membered ring system¹⁵. The peak at 1785 cm⁻¹ in all these compounds is due to a ν -lactone anticipated to be exceptionally good hydrogen bond acceptor¹⁶. The enolic hydroxyl is located around 3050 cm⁻¹. The ¹H nmr spectra of 3 reveal signals for H_a and H_b at δ 2.9–3.2 (2H, d), H_c around δ 5.6–6.0 (1H, d) and H_d around δ 3.8 (1H, m). The signal at δ 3.2 is due to benzylmethylene. The aromatic proton of the main skeleton is located at δ 6.4–6.5 (1H, m) and the side-chain aromatic protons are around δ 7.2–7.5 (5H, m, benzyloxy). The vinyl proton at position-3 is identified at δ 5.4 (1H, s) and the enolic proton at δ 12.2. There are some minute deviations in chemical shifts from the values identified by